

Understanding the Age of the Universe: Five Minutes with High-School Physics

Alexandre Amalric
Columbia University
[ORCID: 0009-0000-0685-5868](https://orcid.org/0009-0000-0685-5868)

December 16, 2025

Abstract

Where do we come from?

This short technical note derives a closed-form estimate of the actual consensus age of the universe, which is about [13.8 billion years](#). I only use high-school physics : Newtonian mechanics and energy conservation.

My goal is to show how a seemingly complex cosmological question can be made transparent through simple reasoning and clear exposition.

Contents

1 How Astronomers Measure Cosmic Expansion	1
2 High-School Physics Energy Formula	2
3 Simple Uniform Sphere Universe Model	3
4 Rewinding Cosmic Time to Big Bang	3
5 Conclusion: Numerical Estimate	3

1 How Astronomers Measure Cosmic Expansion

Thanks to the *Hubble Space Telescope*, astronomers can measure how fast the universe expands and thus quantify the **Hubble constant** H_0 from which we can determine the **Hubble time**

$$t_H \equiv \frac{1}{H_0} \approx 14 \text{ billion years}, \quad (1)$$

a first “ballpark” estimate of the universe’s age. A cosmic model would give us the theoretical time of the universe

$$t_0 = C \times \frac{1}{H_0}, \quad (2)$$

using C is a dimensionless number that depends on cosmic ingredients. My goal is to derive C using only high-school physics.

2 High-School Physics Energy Formula

(Annotated for first-time readers)

The high-school mechanical constant energy under gravity is

$$E = \frac{1}{2} m v^2 - \frac{\underbrace{G}_{\text{Newton's constant}} \underbrace{m}_{\text{mass of the universe}} \underbrace{M}_{\text{mass of the universe}}}{\underbrace{R}_{\text{size of the universe}}}, \quad (3)$$

with $v \equiv dR/dt$ the expansion speed of the universe.

Reading the two right-hand-side terms: The first term is the kinetic energy needed to drive expansion whereas the second is the gravity that resists it.

$$E = \frac{1}{2} m v^2 - \frac{G m M}{R}. \quad (4)$$

No external “engine” in our universe choice for the energy constant. To model an expansion explained only by the matter in our universe (self-gravitating balance corresponds to the *Einstein-de Sitter universe* (1932)) we take the *minimal-energy* case with $E = 0$:

$$0 = \frac{1}{2} m v^2 - \frac{G m M}{R}. \quad (5)$$

The reasoning above is deliberately written in a very familiar, high-school style, using the mechanical energy of a test mass m so that standard textbook formulas can be applied directly. A more rigorous formulation would instead work with the *specific energy* (energy per unit mass) of the universe, which is also conserved.

Since the test mass m plays no physical role in the cosmic dynamics, we therefore divide by m immediately:

$$\frac{1}{2} v^2 - \frac{GM}{R} = 0. \quad (6)$$

Then

$$\frac{1}{2} v^2 = \frac{GM}{R} \implies \left(\frac{v}{R}\right)^2 = \frac{2GM}{R^3}. \quad (7)$$

Define $H(t)$ the Hubble instantaneous expansion rate of the universe

$$H(t) \equiv \frac{v}{R}, \quad (8)$$

to obtain the *Newtonian (high-school version of) Friedmann* form

$$\boxed{H^2 = \frac{2GM}{R^3}}. \quad (9)$$

(If you want to compare with the actual complex relativistic *Friedmann equations...*)

3 Simple Uniform Sphere Universe Model

We will model the entire universe as one big, uniform sphere of radius R . The volume of this sphere (measured in cubic meters (m^3)) is given by

$$V = \frac{4}{3}\pi R^3. \quad (10)$$

To obtain the total mass M of the sphere in kilograms (kg), we multiply by the density ρ in kilograms per cubic meter (kg m^{-3}), so that the units of volume cancel ($\text{kg m}^{-3}\text{m}^3 = \text{kg}$) and this gives the total mass:

$$M = \frac{4}{3}\pi R^3 \rho. \quad (11)$$

In this "cosmic sphere", the enclosed mass remains constant over time t :

$$M(t) = \frac{4}{3}\pi R^3(t) \rho(t) = M_0 = \text{constant}. \quad (12)$$

As $R(t)$ increases (expansion), the density must fall so that $M(t)$ still equals M_0 :

$$\frac{4}{3}\pi R^3(t) \rho(t) = \frac{4}{3}\pi R_0^3 \rho_0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \boxed{\rho(t) = \rho_0 \left(\frac{R_0}{R(t)}\right)^3}. \quad (13)$$

Substitute $M_0 = \frac{4}{3}\pi \rho_0 R_0^3$ into (9):

$$H^2 = \frac{2G}{R^3} \left(\frac{4}{3}\pi \rho_0 R_0^3\right) = \frac{8\pi G}{3} \rho_0 \left(\frac{R_0}{R}\right)^3. \quad (14)$$

4 Rewinding Cosmic Time to Big Bang

Using $H = v/R = (1/R) dR/dt$, (14) becomes after taking the square root (power one half)

$$\frac{1}{R} \frac{dR}{dt} = \sqrt{\frac{8\pi G}{3} \rho_0} \left(\frac{R_0}{R}\right)^{3/2} \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad R^{1/2} dR = \sqrt{\frac{8\pi G}{3} \rho_0} R_0^{3/2} dt. \quad (15)$$

Integrate explicitly from the bang ($R=0$ at $t=0$) to today (R_0 at t_0):

$$\int_0^{R_0} R^{1/2} dR = \sqrt{\frac{8\pi G}{3} \rho_0} R_0^{3/2} \int_0^{t_0} dt \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{2}{3} R_0^{3/2} = \sqrt{\frac{8\pi G}{3} \rho_0} R_0^{3/2} t_0. \quad (16)$$

Cancel $R_0^{3/2}$ and use $H_0^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3} \rho_0$:

$$\boxed{t_0 = \frac{2}{3H_0}}. \quad (17)$$

We have just derived the well-known " $C = 2/3$ law" of the [Einstein-de Sitter](#) benchmark.

5 Conclusion: Numerical Estimate

Let's use the Hubble constant measured with the Hubble Space Telescope, $H_0 = 70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1} = 2.27 \times 10^{-18} \text{ s}^{-1}$, [this is an astronomer unit... 1 Mpc= 3.0857×10^{22} m.]

$$t_0 = \frac{2}{3H_0} \approx 9.3 \text{ billion years}. \quad (18)$$

Estimated age:
 $t_0 \approx 10$ billion years

Final remark. For a first-principles, high-school-physics derivation, this result is *fair enough*. For your information, the actual consensus value of this $\frac{1}{H_0}$ C constant comes from the full relativistic Lambda Cold Dark Matter (Λ CDM) model, which includes matter and dark energy:

$$t_0 = \frac{1}{H_0} \int_0^\infty \frac{dz}{(1 + \underbrace{z}_{\text{redshift}}) \sqrt{\underbrace{\Omega_m}_{\text{matter}} (1+z)^3 + \underbrace{\Omega_\Lambda}_{\text{dark energy drives cosmic acceleration}}}},$$

These additional parameters make the “cosmic clock” of this advanced model tick faster, hence an older consensus age of the universe of 13.8 billion years compared to our 10 billion year estimate.

Appendix

Modern cosmological age measurement.

- Planck Collaboration (2018), “Planck 2018 results. I. Overview and the cosmological legacy of Planck,” *Astronomy & Astrophysics* **641**, A1. See Table of cosmological parameters, which reports $t_0 = 13.797 \pm 0.023$ Gyr. [PDF](#) / [DOI link](#)

Einstein–de Sitter & the 2/3 factor.

- A. Einstein & W. de Sitter (1932), *On the Relation between the Expansion and the Mean Density of the Universe*, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **18**, 213. [DOI:10.1073/pnas.18.3.213](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.18.3.213)
- University lecture notes deriving $a(t) \propto t^{2/3} \Rightarrow t_0 = 2/(3H_0)$ (see e.g. [Wikipedia summary](#)).

Friedmann–Lemaître background.

- A. Friedmann (1922), *Über die Krümmung des Raumes*, *Z. Phys.* **10**, 377. [DOI:10.1007/BF01332580](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01332580)
- G. Lemaître (1931 English), *A homogeneous universe of constant mass and increasing radius accounting for the radial velocity of extragalactic nebulae*, *MNRAS* **91**, 483. [DOI:10.1093/mnras/91.5.483](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/91.5.483)
- Relativistic context: [Friedmann equations \(overview\)](#).